

Temperature Interpolation of Cross Sections in the Peacock Monte Carlo Code

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ABSTRACT

Peacock is a new, continuous-energy Monte Carlo code being developed at Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (SSP). Recently, temperature interpolation was added to Peacock so that users can simply enter a temperature and accurately model the temperature-dependent changes in neutron cross sections. The use of a unionized energy grid in Peacock has made temperature interpolation very straightforward. First, the methods used for temperature interpolation in Peacock are described. Then, a representative Light Water Reactor (LWR) pincell is used to demonstrate temperature feedback in Peacock and provide preliminary verification of the interpolation methods. Validation of the Peacock temperature interpolation methodology is ongoing.

Keywords: Peacock, Monte Carlo, Temperature, Cross Section

1. INTRODUCTION

Peacock is a continuous-energy Monte Carlo code under development by Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (SSP) [1]. As Peacock is intended for reactor physics modeling in fission-driven systems, accurate modeling of temperature feedback effects is an essential feature of the code. Unlike multi-group neutron transport methods, temperature dependence in continuous-energy neutron transport methods requires special consideration for the underlying neutron physics.

In reactor physics models, temperatures can vary by hundreds to thousands of Kelvin and the resultant cross sections can vary by a few orders of magnitude. One of the most important physical effects to capture is the Doppler broadening of resonances due to thermal motion of nuclei. To demonstrate the significant change in cross sections as a function of temperature, the fission cross section (MT18) of ²³⁵U is shown at several temperatures with data from the Peacock cross section library in Figure 1. The temperature variation and overlap of the resonances at approximately 3.1 eV and 3.6 eV in ²³⁵U are significantly affected by Doppler broadening as shown in Figure 1.

The modeling of temperature dependence of neutron physics in Monte Carlo neutron transport codes is not entirely new, although the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock do introduce innovations. For example, MCNP has allowed Doppler broadening for quite some time via a pre-processing script [2]. MCNP also allows stochastic interpolation (to be discussed further in Section 2.2) of Thermal Scattering Laws (TSLs) easily from the input file [3]. While the temperature feedback models in MCNP are highly accurate, their usage requires several steps of pre-processing the continuous-energy nuclear data and the on-the-fly interpolation and Doppler broadening methods can significantly increase calculation runtime.

Similarly, temperature dependence has been incorporated into the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code [4]. Temperature feedback in Serpent 2 contains several physical models, including a Doppler broadening pre-processor, stochastic interpolation for TSLs, and interpolation of cross sections in the Unresolved Resonance Region (URR) using the probability tables method [5, 6, 7]. Serpent also includes a method

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Figure 1. Temperature Dependence of Fission Cross Section in ^{235}U .

for Thermal Motion Sampling (TMS) that is unique to the delta-tracking neutron transport method and therefore cannot be directly compared to the methods in Peacock (which employs the surface-tracking method) [8]. While the methods in Serpent are comprehensive, they still require users to consider the different neutron physics modeling options rather than simply asking users to specify a material temperature.

Peacock has been designed to be user-friendly for reactor physics analysis. As such, the user need only specify a material temperature and the necessary temperature interpolation is performed automatically. Furthermore, the continuous-energy methods in Peacock were designed to enable efficient modeling of temperature dependence. Peacock includes models for temperature interpolation of “smooth” cross sections for Doppler broadening, TSLs, and for probability tables in the URR. All of these interpolation methods are detailed herein.

After describing the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock, a pincell problem is used to demonstrate the temperature feedback for a realistic Light Water Reactor (LWR). These demonstration calculations serve to verify the proper implementation of the temperature interpolation in Peacock and also show how this capability can be used for answering realistic questions in reactor physics.

2. TEMPERATURE INTERPOLATION METHODS

Temperature interpolation was a planned feature in Peacock from the earliest stages of development. As such, the structure of the Peacock continuous-energy nuclear data library was designed to permit efficient interpolation.

Peacock performs continuous-energy neutron transport using a unionized energy grid. The energy grid is generated with a proprietary Grid Unionization and Thinning (GUT) methodology which is based on earlier work by Leppänen with additional heuristics designed for fission-driven systems [7]. Unique to Peacock, the energy grid is unionized at the time of library generation. Therefore, the number of energy points is known before runtime and memory requirements for all cross sections and temperatures can be calculated at the time that the library is generated. To ensure that the temperature interpolation method in Peacock has a minimal effect on runtime, necessary cross sections are stored in memory at the temperatures required by the problem. Whenever possible, nuclide data is shared with different

materials for materials of the same temperature and/or temperature-independent data (e.g., secondary particle distributions).

Generally, temperature interpolation will be performed between two bounding temperature points in the pre-computed continuous-energy cross section library. Currently, Peacock allows linear-interpolation between temperatures or square-root-interpolation between temperatures. Some work has suggested that logarithmic-interpolation may be beneficial for temperature-dependent cross section reconstruction [9].

Square-root-interpolation is generally preferred as the square-root dependence captures a dominant component of the Doppler broadening kernel [3]. Preliminary investigations with Peacock have suggested that square-root-interpolation performs better in general than linear-interpolation even in energy regions without resonances. Therefore, square-root-interpolation is used in all of the results presented in this work.

Temperature interpolation in Peacock is divided into three energy-dependent components: “smooth” cross sections where Doppler broadening is the dominant effect, TSLs, and probability tables in the URR. Each of these regions are treated separately.

2.1. Smooth Cross Sections

The “smooth” cross sections are so-called as they do not contain discontinuities (e.g., Bragg edges) and are not probabilistic (e.g., the URR). Smooth cross sections do include resonances.

The GUT methodology in Peacock is used to unionize all energy grids across all temperatures in the continuous-energy cross section library. After the GUT method has been applied to the nuclear data, temperature interpolation in Peacock is performed with essentially a series of table lookups. Consider reaction x for nuclide n ; at energy point p in the unionized energy grid, the smooth cross section can be interpolated as

$$\sigma_{x,p}^n(T) \approx w(T) (\sigma_{x,p,i+1}^n - \sigma_{x,p,i}^n) + \sigma_{x,p,i}^n \quad (1)$$

where temperature T is between the bounding temperature points from the library such that $T_i < T \leq T_{i+1}$. The interpolation weight $w(T)$ is computed using either a linear- or square-root-interpolation as

$$w_{\text{square-root}}(T) = \frac{\sqrt{T} - \sqrt{T_i}}{\sqrt{T_{i+1}} - \sqrt{T_i}} \quad \text{or} \quad (2)$$

$$w_{\text{linear}}(T) = \frac{T - T_i}{T_{i+1} - T_i}. \quad (3)$$

It is noted that the interpolation of smooth cross sections in Peacock resembles temperature interpolation of multi-group cross section data from traditional multi-group lattice physics methods. This simplified cross section interpolation in Peacock is enabled by the fact that the GUT methodology is used to unionize the continuous-energy neutron transport energy grid across all temperatures in the cross section library.

Outgoing particle distributions are all independent of temperature with the exception of elastic scattering (MT2). For all temperature-independent outgoing particle distributions, a single copy is stored in a memory pool and pointers are used to share the memory to prevent duplicate storage. The threshold for using the free-gas approximation for sampling of the target velocity in Peacock is not temperature-dependent, so that is not a concern. Rather than using a temperature-dependent value for the free-gas approximation threshold, Peacock simply uses a suitably high value (typically 1 keV). Then, the target velocity is sampled using the correct nuclide temperature, T , as appropriate.

2.2. Thermal Scattering Laws (TSLs)

TSLs (sometimes called $S(\alpha, \beta)$ tables) are used to describe neutron scattering physics at relatively low neutron energies (typically < 4 eV) when the neutron energy is on the same order as the chemical binding energy of a crystal or molecule. In typical LWRs, a TSL is required for accurately modeling light water.

The temperature dependence of TSLs can be considered to have two components: a cross section part and associated outgoing particle distributions. In Peacock, the same cross section interpolation from Section 2.1 is used to treat the temperature dependence of the cross sections associated with TSLs.

The outgoing particle distributions for TSLs can strongly depend on the material temperature. In Peacock, these outgoing particle distributions are treated using stochastic interpolation, similar to other Monte Carlo codes [3, 6, 10]. Stochastic interpolation is performed by computing an interpolation weight from Eq. (2) or Eq. (3) as appropriate. Then, a uniformly distributed random number, $\xi \in [0, 1)$ is sampled. If $\xi < w(T)$, then the outgoing particle distribution corresponding to temperature T_{i+1} is used. Otherwise, the outgoing particle distribution corresponding to temperature T_i is used.

2.3. Unresolved Resonance Region (URR)

The URR is a region where the underlying resonances cannot be resolved using present analysis methods. Each nuclide has a different URR and these are typically found at intermediate energies in the range of 10 keV to 100 keV.

The conventional method for modeling neutron cross sections in the URR is the probability tables method. For a given set of probability tables, the value of cross section is stochastic and is sampled during the neutron transport calculation.

While it would be possible to interpolate the cross section between two temperatures as in Section 2.1, this would double the number of times a probability table has to be evaluated [7]. In Peacock, the fact that the underlying cross section is, itself, probabilistic is leveraged for the advantage of computational efficiency. When evaluating the cross section in the URR in Peacock, the cross section is stochastically interpolated using the same random number that will be used to evaluate the probability tables.

3. DEMONSTRATION RESULTS

To demonstrate the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock, a representative pincell model is used. This pincell is based on the Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications (VERA) core physics benchmark #1 [11]. This problem is a pincell with UO_2 fuel enriched to 3.1% ^{235}U by mass, a helium gap, and zirconium cladding. The water moderator contains 1300 ppm boron by mass. The fission reaction rate distribution for this representative pincell is shown in Figure 2.

In the results presented here, only the evaluated cross section temperatures are modified. None of the results in this work account for density changes or thermal expansion associated with temperature changes. In this way, these results demonstrate the effect of the temperature-dependent cross section feedback, but do not represent realistic physical models. All calculations here were performed with 50 inactive cycles, 100 active cycles, and one-million particles per cycle. For all results presented here, the one-standard-deviation uncertainty in k_{eff} was less than 8 pcm.

3.1. Doppler Effect

The representative pincell model was used to investigate the Doppler effect in the fuel and observe the temperature feedback on k_{eff} . For this investigation, the temperature was varied in 10 K increments from

Figure 2. Pincell Fission Reaction Rate.

(a) k_{eff} as a Function of Fuel Temperature.

(b) Difference due to Temperature Interpolation.

Figure 3. Doppler Effect in Representative LWR Pincell.

293 K to 600 K. It is expected that the Doppler broadening of resonances in this range of temperatures will be the most extreme encountered in typical reactor physics modeling.

To demonstrate the accuracy of the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock, two cross section libraries were generated: a “coarse” library with the default temperature discretization and a “fine” library with additional temperature points. The coarse library contains cross section data at 293 K and 600 K for all nuclides and additional data at 450 K for important heavy nuclides with large absorption resonances (e.g., ^{235}U and ^{238}U). The fine library contains cross section data at 293 K, 375 K, 450 K, 525 K, and 600 K for all nuclides. By comparing the results of Peacock cases with the fine and coarse cross section libraries, the accuracy of the temperature interpolation methods can be estimated.

Results of the Doppler effect calculations with Peacock are shown in Figure 3. The fine and coarse temperature results in Figure 3a were run with the probability tables disabled to observe the effect of interpolating only the smooth cross sections. Then, the cases were rerun with the coarse temperature library and probability tables enabled (labeled “ptables” in Figure 3a). The probability tables in the URR do not significantly affect the reactivity in this case and k_{eff} varies smoothly with temperature both with and without the probability tables enabled. Evaluating the temperature dependence of the cross sections in the URR has been noted to be a difficult feat and is an ongoing effort in Peacock [7].

(a) k_{eff} as a Function of Moderator Temperature.

(b) Difference due to Temperature Interpolation.

Figure 4. Pseudo-MTC in Representative LWR Pincell.

The absolute difference between k_{eff} with the coarse and fine temperature discretizations is shown in Figure 3b. For this pincell problem in the temperature range where the Doppler effect changes the most rapidly with temperature, all of the calculations computed with the coarse and fine temperature libraries agree within 30 pcm. Figure 3b also shows that the difference between these temperature discretizations is on the order of the uncertainty in k_{eff} as computed with Peacock.

As the cross sections are stored in memory at their interpolated values, the neutron transport kernel is minimally affected by the temperature interpolation method. Therefore, runtime in Peacock is minimally affected by temperature interpolation for these smooth cross sections. For the results in Figure 3, all runtimes differed by $< 0.7\%$ and the impact on runtime is considered to be statistically insignificant.

3.2. Pseudo-Moderator Temperature Coefficient

The temperature interpolation in Peacock was then used to investigate the pseudo-Moderator Temperature Coefficient (MTC); that is, the temperature feedback of the cross section in the moderator. This is only the pseudo-MTC as it does not account for the density change in the water as a function of temperature.

Again, these calculations were performed with the coarse and fine temperature libraries to quantify the accuracy of the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock. As the TSL for light water is a significant reactivity effect in the moderator, this investigation was performed with and without the TSL enabled. The complexities of the physics described by the TSLs do not permit arbitrary regeneration of them on a finer temperature grid. Instead, the TSL is enabled and a smooth change in k_{eff} as a function of temperature is desired (similar to the probability tables in the URR from Section 3.1).

The results of the temperature interpolation investigation of the pseudo-MTC are shown in Figure 4. As expected, Figure 4a shows that the TSL has a significant reactivity effect in the moderator. The value of k_{eff} calculated with Peacock is shown to be reasonably smooth in Figure 4a. Figure 4b shows that the difference between the values calculated with the fine temperature discretization agree very well with those calculated with the coarser temperature discretization.

As temperature interpolation of the TSLs is performed stochastically, it will have some impact on runtime. This impact can be quantified by comparing a case at which the TSL was interpolated (e.g., 590 K)

to a case where the TSL was provided in the nuclear data without interpolation (e.g., 600 K). For the results in Figure 4, the runtime impact of the TSL interpolation was about 3 %.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The capabilities of Peacock, the new continuous-energy Monte Carlo code being developed at SSP, have recently been extended with temperature interpolation for neutron cross sections. As Peacock is intended for reactor physics applications, the ability to evaluate cross sections at temperatures between library points is essential.

The temperature interpolation methods in Peacock were first detailed. In Peacock, the temperature dependence of the cross sections and outgoing particle distributions are treated slightly differently in three different energy regions: smooth cross sections, TSLs, and the URR with probability tables. After describing the temperature interpolation methods in Peacock, a representative LWR pincell model was used to demonstrate the Doppler effect in the fuel and the pseudo-MTC in the moderator (without accounting for changes in density).

All results presented in this work serve to verify the interpolation of temperature-dependent nuclear data in Peacock. That is, all of these results have been code-to-code comparisons with Peacock using neutron cross section libraries with different temperature fidelities. In the future, work will continue with Peacock to validate the results compared to measurements rather than calculations.

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